

Women's Rights – Constitutional Rights and Legal Protection

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Abstract: -

We are all humans, men and women are equal to share in human rights. Although the constitution of India grants men and women equal rights, gender disparities remain. Gender discrimination mostly in favor of men in areas. In the past, human rights had been conceptualized in a way that did not take account of women's lives and the fact they experienced violence, crime, discrimination and coercion. In the past, women followed certain norms and traditions that put many restraints upon them, primarily in the male dominated society. The work of activists, human rights mechanisms and states has been critical in ensuring that the human rights framework has developed and adjusted to summarize the gender specific dimensions women in a better way. Efficiently ensuring women's human rights requires a wide-ranging understanding of the fundamental societal structures and power relations that define and stimulate the ability of the women to enjoy human rights. These power structures have an impact on all aspects of life, from law and politics, to economic and social policy, family and community life, education, training, skill development and attainment of employment opportunities. Rights are universally accepted that means without any discrimination on the basis of caste, color, sex and religion must provide. Its aim is human dignity, equality, liberty and fraternity. This paper views to highlight the problems which are facing by the women and though rights are given by the constitution of India.

Keywords: Women Rights, Violations, Legal Rights and constitutional Rights

Introductions: -

Swami Vivekananda, quoted that, "There is no chance for the welfare of the world unless the condition of women is improved, and it is not possible for a bird to fly on only one wing." Thus, in order to achieve the status of a developed country, India needs to transform its colossal women force into an effective human resource and this is possible only through proper awareness of women rights.

India, the land of goddesses where women are to be respected with high esteem, witnesses' harassment, abuse and other atrocities and crimes against women. Historical study clearly reveals that the status of women in India has been subject to many changes over the span of recorded Indian history. During the Indo-Aryan era of the ancient India's period, women underwent subordination. Practices and taboos like female infanticide, child marriage, dowry and taboo on widow remarriage had a long duration in India paving way for difficult situation in rooting out of Hindu society in northern India. A phenomenal change happened during the British rule when they enacted measures which aimed at removing social taboos, including Bengal sati Regulation, 1829, Hindu Widow's Remarriage Act, 1856, Female Infanticide Prevention Act, 1870 and Age of Consent Act, 1891. Women's rights under the Constitution of India mainly include equality, dignity, and freedom from discrimination: additionally, India has various statues governing the rights of women. One witnessed greater radical changes in the status of women during the recent era where women served in various senior positions in

the Government of India occupying the chair of being the first citizen of India – The president of India. The Real executive- PM, the States's real executive- CM' the speaker of the Loka Sabha and other exceptionally dignified posts. In spite of this, many women in India still face significant difficulties. Violence against women especially sexual violence has been a great threat to the rights of women. Hence, there is a desire for consciousness of the rights which seeks to shield women.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To know the need of women rights.
2. To analyse the various women rights in India.
3. To review the government enactments which ensures women rights.
4. Adopt and strengthen sound polices and enforceable for the promotion of gender equality.

Violations of Women's Rights

The areas that violate the Rights of women in India have been stated as follows.

1. **Dowry deaths: -** Day by day dowry death cases are increasing. Because lack of effective implementation of "The dowry prohibition Act", It has been disconnected that mostly number of states neither have a dowry prohibition officers nor do they made it mandatory to keep the record of things given and received.
2. **Missing of Women and Girls: -** All over the world women and girls are missing for one or other purpose.
3. **Domestic Violence: -** In spite of the protection of women from domestic violence Act 2005, it

is increasing, when a women experiences violent and criminal acts at the hands of their husbands, in laws, fathers, brothers and other family members. These include verbal abuse, physical abuse and inflicting various forms of mistreatment.

4. **Child Marriage:** - Child marriage which deprives the childhood from their education. It effects the social psychological and emotional of the child in a negative way child marriage Act 2006, prohibit child marriage and declares-18 as the marriage age for girls and 21 for boys.
5. **Sati:** - It is practice when the widows were placed in the funeral pyres of their husbands. Through it was abolished by the Social Reformer Raja Ram Mohan Roy. The sati prevention act was passed which declared the practice of sati as a crime.
6. **Preference for a male child:** - People who belongs to rural communities and socio-economically backward sections of the society wants male child. Because they feel and regards male child as a assert to the family. Preference for a male child is historically deep rooted in the patriarchal system of the Indian society. May be agricultural factor, where it considered as major source of income and controlled by male themselves.
7. **Female Foeticides and Female Infanticide:** - Female Foeticide means killing of the girl child before its birth and female infanticide means killing of the girl child after its birth. This practice is very worst, because which deny the basic right from the girl child, that is the right to live.
8. **Education:** - Education must become basic for each and every individual without any discrimination constitution made right to education is obligatory under Article-21, for all irrespective of male and female in the society. But percentage of female in rural areas very less when compared to male child. Many reasons arise for drop-out girls from educational system.
9. **Sexual Harassment at the Workplace:** - Now days, this problem is increasing, because of employment women are discriminated on the basis of pay and remuneration for their jobs, women are mistreated both in rural and urban area in concern towards their promotion and advancement within the employment setting. This sexual harassment compelled the women to leave her job though she needs very badly for her survive in the society.
10. **Rape:** - Now days these cases are rapidly increasing due to animosity, enmity, resentment etc. The upper caste people use mass rapes as a strategy to exercise power over lower caste groups. Through the laws is there, gang rape or

individual rape take place whether inside the home or outside the home.

11. **Forced Evictions and Exclusions:** - In India, widows are evicted from their martial homes and they are meant to look after their needs and requirements on their own, after the death of their husbands. Their children to get evicted along with them, women headed households and women in general are less secure as compared to men. When a woman loses her spouse, there are various types of detrimental consequences that they are supposed to go through. When they are evicted from homes, they are required to face all hardships and difficulties in order to provide for their sustenance. A single woman, with no land or family to take care of often ends up in the urban slum.
12. **Social Violence against Women:** - Patriarchal family made the women difficult to obtain her position and justice in the society especially religious communities have made the life of women miserable due to conservative practices. This made her to stick on the wall of home and she is isolator from the outside world.
Provisions of Violence against women

The rights available to woman in India can be classified into two categories, namely as Constitutional Rights and Legal Rights. The constitutional rights are those which are provided in the various provisions of the constitution. The legal rights on the other hand are those which are provided in the various laws of the parliament and the state legal legislation.

Constitutional Rights to Women in India –

The constitution of India in its attempts to provide equal rights and opportunities to women and to ensure protection and justice has made the following provisions...

1. Constitution assures equality to all its citizens including women. (Article-14)
2. No discrimination against its citizens of India on the basis of sex (Article-15(1))
3. The state is empowered to make any special provision for women. In other words, this provision enables the state to make affirmative discrimination in favors of women (Article-15(3))
4. No discrimination be made by the state against its citizens including women while providing jobs (Article-16)
5. Traffic in human beings and forced labour are prohibited (Article-23(1))
6. The state to secure for men and women equally the right to an adequate means of livelihood (Article 39(a))

7. To fixing “equal pay for equal work” without discriminating between men and women. (Article 39(d))
8. To required to ensure that the health and strength of women workers are not abused and that they are not forced by economic necessity to enter avocations unsuited to their strength (Article 39e)
9. The state shall take it as its responsibility to provide maternity benefits for its women employes (Article 42)
10. Reserving one third of the total number of seats for women in the panchayats for which direct elections are held (Article 243 D (3))
11. Reserving one third of the total number of the presidential posts at all the levels of the panchayat systems (Article 243 D (4))
12. Reserving one third of the total number of seats for women in the town municipalities for which direct elections are held (Article 243(T)(3))
13. Reserving the presidential posts of the town municipalities for women in such manner as the state legislature may provide (Article 243 T (4))
14. It’s promoting harmony and fraternity among people and doing with all the humiliating customs in respect of women (Article 51(A) and e)

Legal Rights to Women

The following various legislations contained several rights and safeguards for women:

1. Hindu Widows’ Remarriage Act, 1856
2. Indian Christian Marriage Act 1872
3. Indian Divorce Act 1869
4. Child Marriage Restraint Act, 1929
5. Dissolution of Muslim marriages Act, 1939
6. Parsi marriage and divorce Act, 1936
7. Special marriage Act, 1954
8. Hindu succession Act, 1956
9. Hindu adoptions and maintenance Act, 1956
10. Immovable traffic(prevention) Act, 1956
11. Hindu marriage Act, 1955
12. Indecent representation of women (prohibition) Act, 1986
13. Maternity benefit Act, 1961
14. Dowry prohibition Act, 1961
15. Medical termination of pregnancy Act, 1971
16. Pre-conception and pre-natal diagnostic techniques. (Prohibition of sex selection)
17. Equal Remuneration Act, 1976
18. Family courts Act, 1984
19. Muslim women Act, 1986 (protection of rights on divorce)
20. National commission for women Act, 1990
21. Protection of women from Domestic Violence Act 2005
22. Indian evidence Act, 1872
23. Indian penal code 1860

24. Sexual harassment for women at workplace Act, 2013 (Prevention, prohibition and redressal)

Conclusions:

The main purpose of this research paper is to acquire understanding of human rights of women. Because women have been undermined is due to the existence of the patriarchal society. In the male dominant society, preference was given to the male children; there were practices of female foeticide and female infanticide. Therefore, not only rights are provided to the women but also protection must be given.

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